

Fraction-resolved pyrolysis behavior, conversion-dependent kinetics, and predictive severity framework for engineered biochars from fig-processing residues

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ABSTRACT

Industrial fig processing generates seed-rich and skin-rich residues that remain underutilized as biochar precursors. This study treated fractionation as a process-design variable by comparing separately recovered fig seed and fig skin under matched pyrolysis conditions and multi-rate thermogravimetric analysis. Across a severity matrix of 350–500 °C with varied heating rates and holding times, biochar yield decreased from 30.3 to 24.52% for fig seed and from 32.0 to 27.73% for fig skin, with fig skin consistently retaining more solid under identical programmes. ATR-FTIR analysis revealed different carbonization pathways: seed-derived chars showed stronger attenuation of O-H and aliphatic C-H bands together with a more pronounced condensed/aromatic region, whereas skin-derived chars retained clearer oxygen-containing features. TG-DTG analysis at 5–40 °C min⁻¹ showed contrasting devolatilization behavior, with fig seed dominated by a broad mid-temperature event and fig skin characterized by an early dominant peak followed by a secondary higher-temperature contribution. Gaussian DTG-stage partitioning converted these differences into quantitative descriptors, with fig skin retaining a persistent Stage I contribution (<260 °C; 27.21–35.54%) and fig seed developing a substantial Stage III fraction (≥400 °C; up to 52.17%). Isoconversional analysis showed higher and more conversion-sensitive apparent activation energies for fig seed (~107–327 kJ mol⁻¹) than for fig skin (~74–151 kJ mol⁻¹). DAEM analysis supported this contrast, while screening gate-to-gate LCA showed that midpoint burdens were governed mainly by programme-level electricity demand, with Program 3 giving the lowest burdens for both fractions. These results support a fraction-specific severity framework for targeted biochar production.

1. Introduction

Figs (*Ficus carica* L.) are widely consumed as fresh fruit and in processed forms such as dried figs, jams, syrups, and bakery ingredients, and are valued for both sensory quality and nutritional and bioactive attributes [1]. Global dried-fig production was reported at ~134,000 t in the 2022/23 season [2], reflecting the scale of industrial handling and processing. Along these value chains, solid side-streams arise from sorting and trimming, peel/skin removal in selected products, and seed-rich pomace generated during pulping or pressing operations [3,4]. Such residues are produced continuously and at high throughput, creating a clear need for robust valorization pathways. Although high-value extraction and fractionation routes exist, they are often

constrained by feedstock variability, solvent/reagent demand, downstream separation complexity, and cost. Thermochemical conversion therefore remains an attractive platform because it tolerates heterogeneous inputs and converts residues into storable carbonaceous solids and energy carriers.

Among thermochemical routes, pyrolysis converts biomass under oxygen-free conditions into a polygeneration slate (biochar, condensable vapours/bio-oil, and permanent gases), enabling simultaneous waste management and resource recovery [5,6]. Biochar is increasingly treated as an engineerable carbon material rather than a simple combustion by-product, because its physicochemical attributes reflect coupled effects of feedstock composition and process severity. In general, increasing pyrolysis temperature promotes deoxygenation and

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carbonization/aromatization, often shifts the solid toward higher alkalinity and thermal stability, and can enhance accessible porosity within a feedstock-dependent severity window, while progressively attenuating oxygenated surface functionality [7]. However, optimization is non-trivial: product distribution and solid quality depend strongly on temperature history and residence conditions that govern volatile evolution and solid-phase maturation, and these sensitivities can become more pronounced for agri-food residues with anatomically distinct fractions that exhibit different devolatilization behaviours and char-forming propensities [8].

Understanding thermal decomposition behaviour is therefore central to process design, scale-up, and reproducible char manufacture. Non-isothermal thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) provides a practical route to interrogate devolatilization pathways and quantify apparent kinetics from TG data collected at multiple heating rates [8–10]. Multi-rate datasets reduce bias associated with single-rate fitting and enable more robust estimation of kinetic descriptors [9,10]. In this context, model-free (isoconversional) approaches such as Flynn–Wall–Ozawa (FWO), Kissinger–Akahira–Sunose (KAS), and Starink are especially useful because they resolve the conversion dependence of the apparent activation barrier, $E_a(\alpha)$, without imposing a single global kinetic form, while Friedman analysis provides a complementary differential view of the same conversion-resolved behavior [9]. For complex biomass pyrolysis, where overlapping sub-reactions evolve with conversion, such descriptors are more defensible as process-oriented indicators than as proof of a unique mechanism [11, 12].

Beyond bulk carbonization, biochar functionality in downstream uses is governed strongly by surface chemistry and the distribution of reactive sites. Biomass-derived carbons can carry oxygen-containing functionalities and acid-site populations that influence interaction strength, catalytic behaviour, and reactivity; for example, the coexistence of Brønsted- and Lewis-type sites has been demonstrated in biomass-derived carbon materials and linked to catalytic pathways [13, 14]. This chemistry dependence is equally important in environmental applications, where adsorption is widely used for contaminant control in water and soil systems. In such cases, biochar performance is governed jointly by pore structure and surface chemistry through mechanisms including pore filling, electrostatic interaction, ion exchange, surface complexation/precipitation, and π - π or hydrogen-bonding interactions, depending on pollutant class and char properties [15–17]. Within this context, fig residues are especially interesting because seeds and skins represent anatomically distinct fractions that may differ in biopolymer domains and inorganic associations, and therefore may not respond similarly to the same pyrolysis window. Such differences can plausibly produce distinct DTG stage structures, conversion-dependent kinetic barriers, and dominant apparent kinetic tendencies, all of which matter when selecting heating rate, peak temperature, and residence time for targeted char properties. Previous work has reported non-isothermal TGA-based kinetics for fig-derived residues such as fig pomace, confirming measurable apparent activation barriers and supporting the usefulness of kinetic analysis for fig-based feedstocks [18]. However, most available studies still treat pomace as a single bulk residue and therefore do not resolve the inherent heterogeneity of industrial fig-processing streams. As a result, fraction-resolved comparisons that explicitly distinguish seed-rich and skin-rich residues, and relate their thermal behavior to practical process-selection implications, remain scarce. Consequently, the literature still provides limited guidance on whether seed and skin should be processed under the same severity envelope or whether distinct thermal windows are needed to achieve comparable carbonization states and functional surfaces.

This study addresses that gap by presenting a fraction-resolved comparison of separately recovered raw fig seed and raw fig skin under identical pyrolysis and multi-rate non-isothermal TGA conditions relevant to biochar production. The aim is not to claim a unique mechanism, but to develop a predictive and decision-oriented

interpretation of fraction-specific pyrolysis behavior. To do so, Gaussian DTG-stage deconvolution was used to quantify overlapping mass-loss contributions and delineate fraction-specific devolatilization windows, while process-oriented DTG descriptors such as FWHM and CPI were used to summarize reactivity concentration and operational intensity. These descriptors were interpreted together with multi-heating-rate isoconversional kinetics (KAS, FWO, Starink, and Friedman), qualitative kinetic screening using generalized master plots, distributed-reactivity modelling, and screening gate-to-gate life-cycle assessment to construct a fraction-specific severity framework for fig residues. Within this scope, the kinetic results are treated as fraction-specific process descriptors rather than evidence of a unique pyrolysis mechanism. Practically, the resulting framework distinguishes operating windows that preferentially promote stronger carbonization/aromatization from those that better preserve oxygenated functionality, thereby supporting fraction-specific selection of heating profiles and severity levels for targeted biochar yield, surface chemistry, and environmental-process trade-offs. In this experimental design, seed-rich and skin-rich fractions were evaluated separately; controlled seed–skin mixtures at defined ratios were not prepared and are therefore recommended for future validation.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Feedstock preparation

Fresh fig fruits were purchased as a single batch from a local market in Istanbul and processed on the same day. The fruits were thoroughly washed with tap water to remove surface impurities, and the outer skins were manually separated. The remaining pulp containing seeds was transferred to distilled water and gently stirred to promote density-based separation. The lighter pulp fraction was removed by decantation, while the denser seeds were allowed to settle and were then collected. Both fractions (fig seeds and fig skins) were repeatedly rinsed with distilled water to remove adhering organic matter, followed by oven drying at 70 °C for 24 h to constant mass. The dried materials were ground separately and sieved to obtain homogeneous powders, which were stored in airtight containers prior to biochar production and subsequent thermochemical and spectroscopic analyses.

2.2. Pyrolysis procedure

Biochars were produced from the prepared fig seed and fig skin powders in a laboratory-scale tubular furnace under an inert N₂ atmosphere. For each run, approximately 1.0 g of dried feedstock was placed as a thin, uniform bed in a ceramic crucible and positioned at the centre of the furnace hot zone. Before heating, the reactor tube was purged with high-purity N₂ for 15 min to remove residual oxygen. Pyrolysis was then carried out under a continuous N₂ flow of ~300 mL min⁻¹ throughout heating, holding, and cooling in order to minimize oxidation. Final temperature, heating rate, and residence time were controlled using the furnace programmable PID controller. At the end of the holding period, the furnace was switched off and allowed to cool naturally to room temperature under continued N₂ flow. A parametric matrix was applied by varying final temperature, heating rate, and holding time within the ranges 350–500 °C, 10–25 °C min⁻¹, and 15–60 min, respectively, as summarized in Table 1. Biochar samples were coded as F-SD1–F-SD5 for fig seed and F-SN1–F-SN5 for fig skin, where the numeral denotes the ordered condition set from lower to higher thermal severity.

2.3. Thermogravimetric analysis and kinetic modelling

Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) was used to characterize the thermal decomposition behavior of the raw (dried and ground) fig seed and fig skin feedstocks. Approximately 5 mg of sample was loaded into

Table 1
Matched pyrolysis programme matrix for fig seed and fig skin residues.

Programme	Fig seed code	Fig skin code	Temperature (°C)	Heating rate (°C min ⁻¹)	Holding time (min)
P1	F-SD1	F-SN1	350	10	60
P2	F-SD2	F-SN2	400	10	30
P3	F-SD3	F-SN3	400	25	20
P4	F-SD4	F-SN4	450	10	15
P5	F-SD5	F-SN5	500	15	15

an alumina crucible and analyzed using a TA Instruments SDT Q600 simultaneous thermal analyzer (TA Instruments, New Castle, DE, USA) under a nitrogen atmosphere at 50 mL min⁻¹. The temperature was increased from ambient to 700 °C at heating rates (β) of 5, 10, 20, and 40 °C min⁻¹, and the TG and DTG signals were recorded continuously.

To estimate the conversion-dependent apparent activation energy without assuming a predefined reaction model, four model-free iso-conversional methods were applied: Kissinger-Akahira-Sunose (KAS) [19,20], Flynn-Wall-Ozawa (FWO) [21,22], Starink [23], and Friedman [24] methods were employed. For each conversion level, temperature values obtained at different β were used to construct the standard linear forms:

$$\text{KAS method : } \ln \left(\frac{\beta}{T^2} \right) = \ln \left(\frac{A.E}{R.g(\alpha)} \right) - \frac{E}{RT} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{FWO method : } \ln \beta = \ln \left[\frac{A.E}{R.g(\alpha)} \right] - 5.331 - 1.052 \frac{E}{R.T} \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Starink method : } \ln \left(\frac{\beta}{T^{1.92}} \right) = \text{Constant} - 1.0008 \frac{E}{RT} \quad (3)$$

$$\text{Friedman method : } \ln \left(\beta \frac{d\alpha}{dT} \right) = \ln (A.f(\alpha)^n) - \frac{E}{RT} \quad (4)$$

In these equations, β , α , and T represent the heating rate (K min⁻¹), conversion, and absolute temperature (K), respectively. A , E , and R represent the pre-exponential factor (min⁻¹), apparent activation energy (J mol⁻¹), and universal gas constant (8.314 J mol⁻¹ K⁻¹), respectively. The term $f(\alpha)$ denotes the reaction model function and $g(\alpha)$ its integral form. In the Friedman equation, n is the reaction order parameter.

To resolve overlapping decomposition regimes, DTG rate signals were analyzed over 150–500 °C using a Gaussian-mixture representation [25]. After applying a non-negative rate convention, the rate signal was represented as:

$$g_i(T) = a_i \exp \left[- \frac{(T - T_{p,i})^2}{2\sigma_i^2} \right] \quad (5)$$

Where a_i , $T_{p,i}$, and σ are the peak amplitude, peak temperature, and width parameter of component i , respectively. Stage contributions (Stage I–III) were obtained by normalizing the component areas and assigning the components according to their peak temperatures [26]. Additional DTG-derived descriptors, including the full width at half maximum (FWHM) and the comprehensive pyrolysis index (CPI), were used to summarize the localization and operational intensity of devolatilization in DTG space [27]. These descriptors were used as process-oriented indicators complementary to the conversion-dependent kinetic analysis rather than as evidence of a unique mechanism. The detailed parameter definitions and extraction procedure for CPI are provided in Supplementary File S1, Section S2.6. The CPI was calculated as:

$$\text{CPI} = \frac{r_{\max} r_{\text{mean}} \Delta m_{\text{active}}}{T_{p,K} T_{s,K} \Delta T_{1/2}} \quad (6)$$

The generalized (Criado-type) differential master-plot [28] was applied in reduced form using a reference conversion of $\alpha = 0.5$:

$$\frac{\left(\frac{d\alpha}{d\theta} \right)}{\left(\frac{d\alpha}{d\theta} \right)_{\alpha=0.5}} = \frac{f(\alpha)}{f(0.5)} \quad (7)$$

where, α is conversion, θ is the generalized time, and $f(\alpha)$ is the candidate kinetic model function used to generate the theoretical master curves. In the present work, generalized master plots were used as a qualitative screening tool within restricted conversion windows rather than for assigning a unique kinetic mechanism. In addition, a DAEM-based predictive analysis was performed on the multi-rate TG data of raw fig seed and raw fig skin using global fitting together with leave-one-heating-rate-out validation. Full equations, fitting workflow, and validation metrics are provided in Supplementary File S1.

2.4. Characterization of biochar samples

The raw fig residues (fig seed and fig skin) and their derived biochars were characterized to evaluate the chemical and structural changes induced by pyrolysis. ATR-FTIR spectroscopy and thermogravimetric measurements were used to assess functional-group evolution and fuel-related properties. Surface functional groups were analyzed by ATR-FTIR spectroscopy over the range of 4000–500 cm⁻¹ at a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹ using 32 scans per sample. The resulting spectra were used to monitor the attenuation of oxygen-containing bands and the development of aromatic/condensed carbon features with increasing pyrolysis severity.

Fuel-related properties were determined by proximate analysis, including volatile matter, fixed carbon, and ash content, using a TA Instruments SDT Q600 thermogravimetric analyzer following established procedures. On the basis of the proximate data, the ultimate composition (C, H, O, and N) and higher heating value (HHV) were estimated using published proximate-to-ultimate and HHV correlations. For brevity, the correlation equations together with the complete set of derived indices and ratios, including fuel ratio, energy densification ratio, energy yield, carbon retention, atomic H/C and O/C ratios, and deoxygenation metrics, are provided in Supplementary File S2. A screening gate-to-gate life-cycle assessment (LCA) was performed in OpenLCA to compare the five pyrolysis programmes. Electricity consumption was treated as the dominant foreground input, and midpoint indicators were used for comparative evaluation of programme-level environmental burdens.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Effect of pyrolysis conditions on biochar yield and fuel-property evolution

Biochar yields from fig seed and fig skin varied across the five pyrolysis programs (Fig. 1), indicating that solid recovery was governed by the combined effects of peak temperature, heating rate, and residence time. The mildest program (350 °C, 10 °C min⁻¹, 60 min) produced the highest yields, reaching 30.3% for fig seed (F-SD1) and 32.0% for fig skin (F-SN1), where lower thermal severity limited secondary cracking and volatile release, thereby preserving more solid residue while decomposition remained dominated by hemicellulose/cellulose devolatilization, with lignin degrading over a broader range [29]. As the overall thermal intensity increased within the tested matrix, biochar yield declined in both fractions, reaching minima at 500 °C (15 °C min⁻¹, 15 min), with values of 24.52% for fig seed (F-SD5) and 27.73% for fig skin (F-SN5). Across all matched programs, fig skin consistently produced more char than fig seed by approximately 1.7–3.2%, indicating a greater tendency toward solid retention under identical thermal

Fig. 1. Biochar yield (%) of fig seed (a) and fig skin (b) under different pyrolysis conditions.

histories. This behavior is consistent with the higher ash/inorganic fraction of the raw skin feedstock (Table 2), which can contribute to residual mass and promote char formation.

Proximate-derived indices further confirm systematic fuel upgrading after pyrolysis (Table 2). The raw feedstocks were volatile-rich (F-SD-Raw: VM 76.37%; F-SN-Raw: VM 68.14%), with relatively low fixed carbon contents (19.24–23.26%) and modest HHV values (19.54–20.19 MJ kg⁻¹). Following pyrolysis, volatile matter decreased sharply to 12.22–24.35%, while fixed carbon increased to 62.55–74.50%, indicating extensive devolatilization and progressive enrichment of the solid carbon matrix [30]. Consistent with this transition, HHV increased to 27.43–29.57 MJ kg⁻¹ and the energy densification ratio (EDR) rose to 1.36–1.51. The fuel ratio (FR = FC/VM) increased from 0.25 to 0.34 in the raw residues to 2.57–6.10 in the biochars, confirming intensified carbonization [31]. The most carbonized sample within the skin series was F-SN3 (FR = 6.10), whereas F-SN4 showed the least advanced carbonization (FR = 2.57) because of its higher retained volatile fraction [32]. Overall, these trends show that increasing severity did not simply reduce yield, but also shifted the products toward more carbon-dense and energy-enriched solids.

Retention-based indices highlight the central trade-off of the process. The mildest program (F-SD1 and F-SN1) maximized both energy yield (EY = 43.78–45.06%) and carbon retention (CR = 44.64–45.83%), whereas more severe programs reduced these values despite continued improvement in HHV and carbonization intensity (e.g., F-SD5 and F-SN5; EY = 35.64–38.18% and CR = 36.36–38.81%) [33]. Thus, the tested matrix separates two different performance objectives: mild conditions favor maximum solid recovery and retained energy/carbon, whereas intermediate-to-higher severity favors stronger upgrading of the char matrix. This distinction is also reflected in the estimated

elemental trends. The highest carbon content was observed for F-SD4 (C = 80.45%), the maximum fuel ratio for F-SN3 (FR = 6.10), the highest carbon retention for F-SN1 (CR = 45.83%), and the greatest O/C reduction for F-SD3 (88.37%). By contrast, F-SN4 exhibited the highest H/C (0.519) and O/C (0.138), indicating the least advanced carbonization and the greatest persistence of oxygenated character among the produced biochars [34]. These results are consistent with the well-established effect of pyrolysis severity in lowering H/C and O/C through deoxygenation and aromatic condensation, which is commonly associated with increasing structural stability [35]. Taken together, these results indicate that the preferred operating window depends on the intended process objective: mild conditions favor maximum solid recovery and retained energy/carbon, whereas intermediate-to-higher severity favors stronger carbonization and fuel upgrading. This yield–quality tradeoff provides the first process-design basis for distinguishing seed-rich and skin-rich fig residues within the fraction-specific severity framework developed in the subsequent thermal, kinetic, and predictive analyses.

3.2. ATR–FTIR analysis of raw fig residues and derived biochars

ATR–FTIR spectra (Figs. 2 and 3) were used to interpret how surface chemistry evolves during pyrolysis of fractionated fig residues produced under an identical operating matrix. Both fractions show the expected progression from oxygenated, biomass-like signatures toward a more condensed carbon structure, evidenced by attenuation of broad O–H and aliphatic C–H bands and increasing prominence of bands within the ~1500–1600 cm⁻¹ region commonly associated with condensed/aromatic structures during thermal treatment [36,37]. However, seed and skin do not evolve identically under matched severity, indicating fraction-dependent carbonization pathways and supporting residue fractionation as a process-design variable.

Raw seed (Fig. 2) exhibits oxygenated biomass features, including O–H (~3291 cm⁻¹), aliphatic C–H (~2923 cm⁻¹), a strong carbonyl band (~1743 cm⁻¹), and C–O stretching near ~1157 cm⁻¹ [38,39]. Following pyrolysis (F-SD1→F-SD5), O–H and aliphatic C–H contributions are strongly suppressed, consistent with dehydration/deoxygenation and removal of labile moieties during devolatilization [40]. Concurrently, the condensed-structure region becomes dominant, with a characteristic maximum at ~1515–1519 cm⁻¹ across the biochars, consistent with progressive structural condensation during char formation [41]. The carbonyl region weakens and shifts toward ~1689–1694 cm⁻¹, consistent with reduced biomass-like carbonyl intensity and persistence of more conjugated carbonyl/carboxyl-associated environments, noting that partial overlap with conjugated/aromatic contributions in this region may occur in chars [40]. C–O-related features in the fingerprint region reorganize and shift upward (~1166–1198 cm⁻¹), consistent with restructuring of oxygen-bearing environments during carbonization [42].

As shown in Fig. 3, raw fig skin exhibits O–H (~3281 cm⁻¹), aliphatic C–H (~2919 cm⁻¹), carbonyl (~1725–1731 cm⁻¹), and C–O

Table 2

Proximate analysis, HHV, and proximate-derived performance indices (EDR, EY, CR, FR) for raw fig residues and the corresponding biochars.

Sample	Volatile matter (%)	Fixed carbon (%)	Ash (%)	HHV (MJ kg ⁻¹)	EDR	EY (%)	CR (%)	FR (=FC/VM)
F-SD1-Raw	76.37	19.24	0.15	19.54	—	—	—	0.25
F-SD1	17.69	68.39	9.09	28.23	1.44	43.78	44.64	3.87
F-SD2	16.68	71.39	7.47	29.08	1.49	39.87	40.68	4.28
F-SD3	12.87	74.45	8.49	29.5	1.51	38.32	39.13	5.78
F-SD4	20.31	70.8	4.15	29.57	1.51	39.71	40.51	3.49
F-SD5	13.85	70.51	10.73	28.4	1.45	35.64	36.36	5.09
F-SN-Raw	68.14	23.26	1.9	20.19	—	—	—	0.34
F-SN1	19.29	68.64	7.81	28.43	1.41	45.06	45.83	3.56
F-SN2	19.72	69.2	6.19	28.91	1.43	41.12	41.84	3.51
F-SN3	12.22	74.5	10.05	29.36	1.45	39.76	40.5	6.1
F-SN4	24.35	62.55	7.37	27.43	1.36	39.14	39.75	2.57
F-SN5	20.33	64.63	8.42	27.8	1.38	38.18	38.81	3.18

Fig. 2. ATR-FTIR spectra of raw fig seed and fig seed biochars (F-SD1–F-SD5).

Fig. 3. ATR-FTIR spectra of raw fig skin and fig skin biochars (F-SN1–F-SN5).

($\sim 1016\text{--}1018\text{ cm}^{-1}$) features typical of oxygenated biomass [42]. After pyrolysis (F-SN1→F-SN5), O–H and aliphatic C–H decrease strongly, while bands in the condensed-structure region intensify, with dominant contributions in the $\sim 1564\text{--}1580\text{ cm}^{-1}$ range and a secondary component near $\sim 1554\text{--}1558\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (notably F-SN2–F-SN3), consistent with severity-driven development of condensed structures [43]. The carbonyl region shifted to weaker bands at $\sim 1670\text{--}1684\text{ cm}^{-1}$, indicating attenuation of biomass-like carbonyl groups together with the persistence or formation of conjugated oxygen-containing environments in the chars [7]. In the fingerprint region, the main C–O band shifted upward to $\sim 1120\text{--}1129\text{ cm}^{-1}$, while an additional contribution near $\sim 1240\text{--}1244\text{ cm}^{-1}$ appeared under the mildest condition, suggesting reorganization toward aryl-oxygen/ether-like environments during the early stages of carbonization [7,44]. Across both fractions, assignments in the fingerprint region should be interpreted cautiously because ash- and mineral-associated contributions may overlap with organic vibrations.

The comparative trends are summarized in Fig. 4. Under identical pyrolysis conditions, seed-derived chars showed stronger decreases in O–H and aliphatic C–H features, together with a more dominant condensed/aromatic band in the $\sim 1500\text{--}1600\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region, indicating comparatively greater aromatic condensation and carbonization

tendency. In contrast, skin-derived chars retained comparatively clearer oxygen-containing signatures, including residual or shifted C=O bands and reorganized C–O/aryl–O features, suggesting a relatively more oxygenated and polar surface character. The different FTIR responses may be linked to differences in organic-matrix resistance, oxygenated domains, and ash/mineral-associated contributions. The stronger condensed/aromatic signature of seed-derived chars may reflect a more thermally resistant carbon-forming matrix, consistent with pseudo-component studies showing higher thermal stability and stronger aromatic-feature persistence in lignin-derived chars during pyrolysis. In contrast, the clearer residual C=O and C–O/aryl–O bands in skin-derived chars may indicate a more labile oxygenated matrix and possible ash/mineral contribution, supported by the higher ash content of raw fig skin [45]. These differences are mechanistically relevant, although they should not be interpreted as direct proof of application performance. Oxygen-containing functionalities are commonly associated with hydrogen bonding, electrostatic interactions, ion exchange, and surface complexation, whereas condensed aromatic domains can favor $\pi\text{--}\pi$ interactions and hydrophobic partitioning in the sorption of aromatic organics [15,16]. In soil systems, oxygen-containing surface groups and charge development are linked to cation retention, while oxidation and ageing can further increase carboxyl abundance and

Fig. 4. ATR–FTIR-based conceptual interpretation of surface-chemistry evolution in fig seed- and fig skin-derived biochars produced under matched pyrolysis programmes.

negative surface charge over time [46]. In anaerobic digestion, buffering behaviour may arise from surface functionality together with inherent alkali/alkaline-earth minerals, whereas electron-transfer facilitation has been associated with redox-active motifs and aromatic/ π -electron structures; however, these effects depend strongly on feedstock composition, pyrolysis severity, and application-specific operating conditions [16,47]. In this context, the FTIR results support the view that fig seed and fig skin follow distinct surface-chemistry evolution pathways and are therefore unlikely to yield equivalent biochar surfaces under the same severity conditions.

3.3. Thermal decomposition behaviour and kinetic analysis of raw fig residues

3.3.1. TG–DTG behaviour ($\beta = 5\text{--}40\text{ °C min}^{-1}$)

Thermogravimetric (TG) and derivative thermogravimetric (DTG) profiles of the raw fig seed and raw fig skin revealed clear feedstock-dependent differences in decomposition behavior under non-isothermal heating. For both residues, increasing the heating rate from 5 to 40 °C min⁻¹ shifted the DTG features toward higher temperatures,

consistent with the expected dynamic-heating response arising from reduced residence time at a given temperature and thermal lag effects [48]. At the same time, the DTG curves remained broad and partially overlapping, indicating that decomposition proceeded through multiple superimposed regimes rather than a single discrete event, thereby supporting the use of conversion-dependent kinetic analysis [11]. Raw fig seed (Fig. 5) exhibited a single broad dominant DTG event centered in the mid-temperature region. The temperature of maximum mass-loss rate increased from approximately 341 °C at 5 °C min⁻¹ to 353 °C at 10 °C min⁻¹, 367 °C at 20 °C min⁻¹, and 383 °C at 40 °C min⁻¹. This progressive right-shift, together with the broad peak shape, indicates an extended devolatilization interval in which overlapping reactions remain active over a relatively wide temperature range (e.g., dehydration, depolymerization/devolatilization of hemicellulosic and cellulosic domains, lignin-derived decomposition, and decarboxylation/decarbonylation). Such behavior is consistent with a more distributed and conversion-sensitive decomposition pathway, where increasingly resistant reactions contribute more strongly at later stages of mass loss [49].

In contrast, raw fig skin (Fig. 6) showed a more distinctly two-stage

Fig. 5. Fig seed pyrolysis a) TG curves, b) DTG curves.

Fig. 6. Fig skin pyrolysis a) TG curves, b) DTG curves.

DTG pattern. A dominant low-temperature peak shifted from approximately 182 °C to 237 °C as the heating rate increased from 5 to 40 °C min⁻¹, while a secondary peak or shoulder shifted from about 315 °C to 348 °C over the same β range. The pronounced early event indicates a greater contribution of thermally labile constituents in the skin fraction (e.g., moisture, light volatiles, extractives, pectin-like components, and hemicellulosic domains), whereas the higher-temperature shoulder reflects decomposition of more resistant structural domains (e.g., cellulose-rich domains and lignin-derived char-forming fractions) accompanied by progressive char formation and solid-phase evolution [50]. Relative to fig seed, the skin fraction therefore followed a more front-loaded devolatilization pathway, with a substantial proportion of mass loss occurring earlier in the heating programme.

Taken together, the TG–DTG results define two contrasting thermal decomposition timelines: fig seed is dominated by a broad mid-temperature event spanning roughly 340–380 °C, whereas fig skin is characterized by an early dominant regime at approximately 180–240 °C followed by a secondary contribution at 315–348 °C. These differences indicate that the dominant decomposition behavior evolves differently with conversion in the two fractions, and that a single global kinetic description would not adequately represent both materials. Accordingly, conversion-dependent treatment of the apparent activation barrier, $E_a(\alpha)$, is warranted for both residues, particularly to distinguish the broader overlap-distributed decomposition of seed from the more staged devolatilization behavior of skin [11].

To provide a fixed-temperature comparison, Fig. 7 presents the

Fig. 7. TG/DTG profiles of raw fig seed (a) and raw fig skin (b), showing stage boundaries, characteristic conversion temperatures, DTG events, residue at 700 °C, and stepwise mass-loss contributions.

stage-wise TG/DTG behavior of raw fig seed and raw fig skin at 20 °C min⁻¹ using boundaries at 150 and 400 °C together with the characteristic temperatures T₅%, T₁₀%, and T₅₀%. Both feedstocks exhibited three broad thermal regions, but their decomposition profiles differed clearly in onset, intensity distribution, and terminal residue. Fig skin showed a larger low-temperature mass loss before 150 °C (≈9.6%) than fig seed (≈4.2%), indicating a stronger release of moisture and/or light volatile fractions during the initial stage. Its principal DTG minimum occurred at a much lower temperature (≈182 °C), and a secondary DTG event appeared near 314 °C, consistent with a more segmented devolatilization pattern. By contrast, fig seed displayed a smaller initial loss and a delayed dominant DTG minimum at ≈342 °C, indicating that its most intense decomposition occurred at substantially higher temperature. The intermediate region accounted for the largest share of mass loss in both materials, reaching ≈54.3% for fig skin and ≈55.9% for fig seed, whereas the final residue at 700 °C was higher for fig skin (≈27.3%) than for fig seed (≈21.1%). Overall, these diagnostic plots reinforce that fig skin undergoes earlier and more segmented thermal degradation, whereas fig seed shows a delayed main devolatilization event and lower terminal residue, consistent with their differing carbonization behaviour during pyrolysis.

3.3.2. DTG feature analysis and peak decomposition (150–500 °C)

To resolve overlap within the DTG profiles, the derivative curves in the 150–500 °C interval were deconvoluted using a three-component Gaussian mixture at each heating rate (Supplementary File S1). DTG deconvolution is commonly employed to separate overlapping thermal events into pseudo-components and to quantify their relative contributions through component-curve areas [48,51]. For both residues, the fitted peak temperatures (T_p) shifted systematically toward higher values with increasing β, in agreement with the established dynamic-heating response in which TG/DTG features move to higher temperatures as the heating rate increases [52]. Within the adopted temperature window and fitting framework, the pseudo-stage partitioning revealed a clear feedstock contrast. Fig skin retained a distinct low-temperature contribution assigned to Stage I (<260 °C), accounting for 27.21–35.54% of the total DTG area, whereas fig seed showed negligible Stage I contribution and instead developed a pronounced late-stage fraction at ≥400 °C (Stage III). For fig seed, this Stage III contribution reached 19.22–52.17% for β = 10–40 °C min⁻¹. These pseudo-stage distributions convert the qualitative TG–DTG timeline differences into quantitative descriptors of how decomposition intensity is distributed across temperature, thereby providing a more reproducible basis for comparing the two fractions [53].

To complement peak deconvolution, additional DTG feature descriptors were extracted over the same temperature interval, including peak width (FWHM) and the comprehensive pyrolysis index (CPI) (Supplementary File S1). Although the T_p trends already show that the dominant devolatilization of fig seed occurs at higher temperature than that of fig skin across all heating rates, the peak-shape descriptors sharpen this distinction further. Fig skin exhibited a narrow and nearly invariant FWHM (≈36–37 °C), whereas fig seed showed substantially broader peaks (≈101–118 °C). This broader peak structure is consistent with stronger overlap of constituent decomposition processes and a more distributed devolatilization pathway in DTG space [54]. CPI increased with heating rate for both residues, but remained consistently higher for fig skin (3.213 × 10⁻⁵ to 2.611 × 10⁻³) than for fig seed (8.799 × 10⁻⁶ to 5.240 × 10⁻⁴), indicating more thermally concentrated devolatilization for the skin fraction under identical extraction criteria. Since CPI-type descriptors are commonly used as operational measures of pyrolysis intensity and generally increase with heating rate when evaluated consistently, the higher CPI values for fig skin support its interpretation as a more front-loaded and concentrated decomposing fraction [55]. In contrast to Ea(α) and model-fitting outputs, which parameterize apparent energetic barriers and kinetic-form tendencies, FWHM and CPI summarize the localization and intensity of

devolatilization directly in DTG space. Together, these descriptors provide a complementary, process-oriented basis for distinguishing the broader, overlap-dominated decomposition of seed from the more concentrated multi-stage behaviour of skin.

3.3.3. Isoconversional kinetics (KAS, FWO, Starink, Friedman)

The isoconversional results revealed a clear contrast between fig seed and fig skin in the evolution of the apparent kinetic barrier during pyrolysis. For fig seed, the three integral methods (KAS, FWO, and Starink) showed strong internal consistency over the full conversion range and all indicated a pronounced rise in Ea with conversion (Table 3). Across α = 0.1 to 0.9, Ea increased from approximately 107–110 kJ mol⁻¹ to 321–327 kJ mol⁻¹, indicating that the dominant decomposition pathway became progressively more energy-demanding as conversion proceeded.

Such an upward Ea(α) trajectory is consistent with complex multi-step solid-state decomposition, in which the dominant contribution to the overall rate changes as conversion proceeds; therefore, Ea(α) is more appropriately interpreted as an effective conversion-resolved barrier than as a single global kinetic constant [56]. The Friedman results follow the same monotonic trend but yield systematically higher Ea values, increasing from 120.87 to 336.07 kJ mol⁻¹. This difference is consistent with the known sensitivity of differential isoconversional methods to rate-measurement uncertainty and local DTG overlap, particularly at conversions where the mass-loss signal changes rapidly or where equivalent conversion points are less sharply defined across heating programs [57].

In contrast, fig skin occupies a substantially lower Ea(α) band and exhibits weaker conversion dependence (Fig. 8). Across the integral methods, Ea increases from about 74 to 77 kJ mol⁻¹ at α = 0.1 to 149–151 kJ mol⁻¹ at α = 0.9, with excellent linearity. The close agreement among KAS, FWO, and Starink across the full conversion range indicates comparatively stable isoconversional behavior for the skin fraction. Comparable Ea magnitudes and similarly moderate conversion dependence have been reported for other biomass residues, including fruit-derived materials, supporting the plausibility of both the absolute values and the comparatively restrained rise observed here [58]. Relative to seed, the skin fraction therefore follows a less heterogeneous kinetic path, with a lower and more weakly varying apparent barrier over α = 0.1–0.9.

Taken together, the isoconversional results indicate that fig seed exhibits a markedly more heterogeneous and conversion-sensitive devolatilization trajectory than fig skin. The seed fraction transitions from relatively accessible early-stage decomposition into progressively more resistant regimes at higher conversion, whereas the skin fraction remains within a lower and more gradually changing Ea(α) band. This distinction is consistent with the TG–DTG and DTG-deconvolution results discussed above: the broad, overlap-distributed DTG structure of seed is mirrored by a strong rise in Ea(α), while the more front-loaded and staged devolatilization pattern of skin is reflected in a lower and more stable activation-energy profile. Accordingly, the two fractions should not be represented by the same overall kinetic description; rather, they require a feedstock-resolved interpretation in which the relative prominence of overlapping sub-processes evolves more strongly with conversion for seed than for skin [12,57].

The combined FTIR, TG/DTG, proximate, and kinetic evidence provides a plausible explanation for the different carbonization pathways of fig seed and fig skin. Seed-derived chars showed stronger aromatic/condensed signatures, consistent with the broader and delayed devolatilization behaviour of raw fig seed and its higher, more conversion-sensitive apparent activation-energy profile. These features suggest that the seed fraction follows a more gradual and resistant decomposition pathway, favouring progressive deoxygenation, secondary char maturation, and condensation into aromatic domains during pyrolysis [7,40,43]. In contrast, fig skin showed earlier and more staged devolatilization, higher terminal residue, and clearer residual or reorganized

Table 3

Isoconversional activation energies (E_a) and linear regression coefficients (R^2) for pyrolysis of raw fig seed determined by KAS, FWO, Starink, and Friedman methods ($\alpha = 0.1-0.9$).

α	KAS		FWO		Starink		Friedman	
	E_a (kJ/mol)	R^2						
0.1	106.96	0.989	110.48	0.991	107.25	0.989	120.87	0.990
0.2	129.79	0.982	132.66	0.985	130.08	0.982	141.08	0.979
0.3	142.39	0.988	145.03	0.990	142.68	0.988	160.67	0.994
0.4	155.36	0.989	157.62	0.991	155.66	0.989	169.00	0.993
0.5	166.78	0.987	168.67	0.989	167.08	0.987	182.46	0.968
0.6	180.45	0.967	181.91	0.970	180.74	0.967	208.80	0.965
0.7	211.97	0.973	212.13	0.975	212.25	0.973	254.17	0.986
0.8	260.43	0.982	258.45	0.983	260.68	0.982	317.19	0.993
0.9	326.34	0.995	321.39	0.995	326.55	0.995	336.07	0.986
Ave.	186.72	—	187.59	—	187.00	—	210.04	—

Fig. 8. Isoconversional plots a)KAS, b) FWO, c) Starink and d) Friedman for Fig skin.

oxygen-containing FTIR features. This behaviour is consistent with a more labile and heterogeneous feedstock structure and a stronger ash/mineral-associated contribution, as also suggested by the higher ash content of raw fig skin compared with raw fig seed. Mineral-associated

domains may influence devolatilization behaviour and contribute to the persistence or overlap of oxygen-containing bands in the fingerprint region [7,42,43,50]. Nevertheless, because detailed lignocellulosic fractionation and mineral speciation were not directly measured, these

proposed drivers should be regarded as integrated, mechanism-oriented interpretations rather than direct compositional evidence. Future work should combine fraction-resolved pyrolysis with cellulose/hemicellulose/lignin quantification, ICP-based mineral profiling, and structural characterization to validate these drivers.

3.3.4. Generalized master-plot analysis (Criado method)

Fig. 9 presents the generalized master plots of raw fig seed and raw fig skin, expressed as the normalized experimental response, $Z(\alpha)/Z(0.5)$, and compared with a representative Avrami–Erofeev reference function. The shaded interval, $\alpha = 0.3–0.6$, was selected as the principal devolatilization window for comparison because it captures the main mass-loss regime while avoiding the low- and high-conversion regions where normalization effects and late-stage instability become more pronounced. This window approximately corresponds to the principal devolatilization region identified from the TG/DTG profiles, but is defined here in conversion space rather than temperature space [59]. The detailed model-ranking results are provided in the Supplementary material. Briefly, within $\alpha = 0.3–0.6$, both fractions showed their closest agreement with power-law (P-type) functions, followed by Avrami–Erofeev (A-type) functions. For clarity, the main-text figure emphasizes the experimental master plots and a representative A-type reference curve, while the full ranking hierarchy and associated error metrics are provided in the Supplementary file 1. This avoids overloading the main-text figure while retaining the key comparison within the active decomposition interval.

For raw fig seed, the experimental master plot approaches the representative A-type trajectory within the principal devolatilization window but diverges progressively outside that interval, particularly at higher conversion. This behavior is consistent with the stronger conversion dependence observed in the isoconversional analysis, where $E_a(\alpha)$ increases markedly with conversion. The broader deviation pattern indicates that the apparent kinetic form changes more strongly as pyrolysis proceeds, suggesting a more pronounced conversion-dependent regime shift once the main volatile-release stage has been exceeded [60]. For raw fig skin, the experimental master plot also departs from the representative theoretical curve beyond the main window, but the deviation pattern is less severe when interpreted together with the supplementary ranking results. This suggests that, under the same normalization and comparison basis, the apparent kinetic behavior of raw fig skin is somewhat more internally consistent than that of raw fig seed within the principal devolatilization interval, even though neither fraction can be represented adequately by a single invariant model across the full conversion range. Overall, the generalized master-plot analysis indicates that both raw fig fractions share a similar apparent

kinetic tendency within the principal devolatilization regime, centered on power-law behavior with Avrami–Erofeev-type behavior as the next closest descriptor. However, the quality of agreement deteriorates outside $\alpha = 0.3–0.6$, especially at high conversion, where the decreasing DTG intensity and the increasing contribution of more refractory solid-phase processes reduce the stability of the apparent kinetic form [60]. In this context, the Criado analysis is most appropriately treated as a qualitative, conversion-window-specific screening tool that complements the isoconversional results and the supplementary model-ranking analysis, rather than as a basis for assigning a unique pyrolysis mechanism.

3.4. Predictive distributed-reactivity modeling of fraction-resolved pyrolysis

The DAEM analysis provided a compact way to interpret the fraction-specific kinetic differences already indicated by the TG-DTG, deconvolution, and isoconversional results, because DAEM is widely used to represent complex pyrolysis as parallel reactions distributed over activation energy [61]. As shown by the global fits in Fig. 10a and b, the TG behavior of both raw fig seed and raw fig skin could not be represented adequately by a single narrow reactivity domain, which is consistent with the use of distributed or multi-component DAEM formulations for complex thermal decomposition systems [61,62]. Instead, both fractions required overlapping distributed-reactivity contributions, but the resulting profiles were clearly different.

For raw fig seed, the fitted DAEM required a broader and more right-shifted activation-energy distribution, with one dominant component centered at approximately $158.1 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ and a second, much broader contribution centered near $154.8 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$. By contrast, raw fig skin showed a distinctly lower-energy and narrower distributed-reactivity pattern, with components centered at about 65.0 and 84.2 kJ mol^{-1} . This contrast is visualized directly in Fig. 11a and b, where the broader combined profile of seed contrasts with the sharper and more localized distribution of skin. The fitted parameters in Table S3.1 further support this interpretation: raw fig seed was characterized by a dominant component with $w_1 = 0.6696$ together with a much broader secondary contribution ($\sigma_2 = 44.2 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$), whereas raw fig skin was represented by lower-energy components with a narrower overall spread. These results indicate that fig seed follows a more heterogeneous devolatilization pathway, whereas fig skin decomposes within a more localized and lower-barrier reactive window.

The predictive behavior of the model further supports this interpretation. The withheld-rate validation shown in Fig. 10c and d preserved the overall mass-loss trajectory and the main seed-skin contrast

Fig. 9. Generalized master plots (Criado method) for raw fig seed (a) and raw fig skin (b), derived from TG/DTG data recorded at heating rates of 5, 10, 20, and $40 \text{ }^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$.

Fig. 10. DAEM representation of TG behavior for raw fig residues. Global multi-rate fits for raw fig seed and raw fig skin are shown in (a) and (b), respectively, while withheld-rate validation results for raw fig seed and raw fig skin are shown in (c) and (d).

Fig. 11. Distributed-reactivity patterns inferred from the selected DAEM and corresponding complexity-validation behavior. Component-wise and combined activation-energy distributions for raw fig seed and raw fig skin are shown in (a) and (b), respectively, while the complexity-validation trade-off is shown in (c).

under unseen heating conditions, in line with the view that DAEM should be judged by predictive performance rather than in-sample fitting alone [63]. For raw fig seed (Fig. 10c), the predicted TG curve closely reproduced the measured profile across the principal devolatilization zone, with only modest deviation in the later stage. For raw fig skin (Fig. 10d), the predicted curve also tracked the measured behavior well, although somewhat larger deviations were visible in the intermediate-to-late conversion region. This predictive ability is also reflected in Table S3.3, where TG-based RMSE values remained within 0.96–1.53% for raw fig seed and 1.34–1.83% for raw fig skin across the withheld-rate cases. Even so, the model retained the essential difference between the two fractions, namely the broader and more delayed devolatilization behavior of seed relative to the more front-loaded response of skin.

The component-wise distributions in Fig. 11a and b help explain these differences physically. In raw fig seed, the combined profile is governed by a narrow dominant component superimposed on a much broader secondary contribution, producing a wider overall reactive envelope. In raw fig skin, one sharp low-energy component dominates the onset region, while the second broader contribution remains comparatively limited, yielding a more concentrated reactivity pattern. The complexity-validation comparison in Fig. 11c further shows that increasing model flexibility improved validation performance for both residues. Consistent with this, Table S3.5 shows that moving from a one-distribution to a two-distribution DAEM substantially reduced overall conversion error for both residues, with overall RMSE α decreasing from 0.0289 to 0.0132 for raw fig seed and from 0.0508 to 0.0177 for raw fig skin. Thus, the selected representation provides a useful balance

between predictive adequacy and interpretability, consistent with recent DAEM studies that evaluate model choice as a trade-off between validation quality and unnecessary complexity [62,63].

This DAEM-based interpretation is also consistent with the independent isoconversional results, which strengthens the kinetic reading in the same way that agreement between DAEM fitting and isoconversional behavior has been used as supportive evidence in prior studies [62]. Raw fig seed showed a stronger increase in $E_a(\alpha)$ with conversion, which agrees with its broader and more heterogeneous distributed-reactivity profile. Raw fig skin remained within a lower and narrower $E_a(\alpha)$ band, matching its narrower DAEM representation. Taken together, these results strengthen the conclusion that the two fractions should not be treated as a single pooled pyrolysis feedstock. Instead, fig seed is associated with a wider severity requirement for complete devolatilization and stronger late-stage resistance, whereas fig skin is associated with earlier mass loss and a more localized decomposition interval.

Overall, the DAEM results add a validated predictive layer to the fraction-specific severity framework developed in this study. Rather than serving as standalone mechanistic proof, they show that the distinct devolatilization behavior of fig seed and fig skin can be captured in a reduced-order distributed-reactivity model with predictive value across unseen heating conditions, thereby strengthening the process-design relevance of the kinetic analysis.

3.5. Screening gate-to-gate life-cycle assessment and environmental implications

A screening gate-to-gate LCA was conducted in OpenLCA using electricity consumption as the dominant foreground input within the adopted process boundary. Under matched pyrolysis programmes, fig seed and fig skin showed very similar midpoint results, indicating that environmental burdens were governed mainly by process energy demand and programme duration rather than by feedstock identity. As shown in Table 4, Program 3 consistently gave the lowest impacts across all reported categories, whereas Program 1 gave the highest. For fig seed, climate-change impacts decreased from 2.653 to 1.003 kg CO₂-eq, resource use, fossils from 29.31 to 11.08 MJ, water use from 1.820 to 0.688 m³ deprivation, acidification from 0.0124 to 0.0047 mol H⁺ eq, and photochemical ozone formation from 0.0051 to 0.0019 kg NMVOC eq from Program 1 to Program 3. Fig skin showed the same overall pattern, with corresponding values decreasing from 2.652 to 1.004 kg CO₂-eq, 29.30 to 11.09 MJ, 1.820 to 0.689 m³ deprivation, 0.0124 to 0.0047 mol H⁺ eq, and 0.0051 to 0.0019 kg NMVOC eq. These close correspondences between the two fractions further support that the midpoint results were driven primarily by programme-level electricity use.

Within this screening framework, Program 3 therefore represents the lowest-burden operating condition among the tested cases. In contrast to the stronger seed–skin differences observed in devolatilization behaviour, kinetic structure, and FTIR evolution, the LCA results were only

weakly sensitive to feedstock fraction under matched programmes. Accordingly, the gate-to-gate LCA should be interpreted as a supporting hotspot-based decision layer for relative programme selection rather than as a full environmental assessment of fig-residue biochar systems. On this basis, Program 3 emerges as the clearest best-compromise operating window when low environmental burden is considered together with favorable carbonization performance. An integrated synthesis of the fraction-resolved yield, thermal, kinetic, predictive, and environmental evidence is provided in Table 5, which summarizes the main decision-support implications of the tested severity matrix for fig seed and fig skin.

4. Conclusions

This study demonstrates that fig-processing residues should not be treated as a single, uniform pyrolysis feedstock. By separating seed-rich and skin-rich fractions and evaluating them under matched pyrolysis and thermal-analysis conditions, the work shows that fractionation itself functions as a process-design variable with direct implications for biochar yield, carbonization pathway, devolatilization structure, and programme-level environmental burden.

Across the applied severity matrix, biochar yields decreased systematically with increasing severity, from 30.3 to 24.52% for fig seed and from 32.0 to 27.73% for fig skin, with skin consistently retaining more solid under matched conditions. ATR–FTIR analysis further showed that the two fractions did not evolve chemically in the same way: seed-derived chars exhibited stronger suppression of O–H and aliphatic C–H features together with a more dominant condensed/aromatic region, whereas skin-derived chars retained comparatively clearer oxygen-containing signatures, indicating a more polar surface chemistry at comparable severity. The raw fractions also exhibited clearly different thermal decomposition structures. TG–DTG analysis showed that fig seed was dominated by a broad mid-temperature devolatilization event, while fig skin followed a more front-loaded pattern characterized by an early dominant peak and a secondary higher-temperature contribution. Gaussian DTG-stage partitioning and DTG-space descriptors reinforced this contrast, with skin maintaining a persistent Stage I contribution and narrow, concentrated DTG behavior, whereas seed developed a substantial late Stage III fraction together with broader, overlap-distributed devolatilization.

Isoconversional kinetics confirmed that these structural differences were accompanied by markedly different apparent barrier profiles. Fig seed occupied a substantially higher and more conversion-sensitive $E_a(\alpha)$ band, whereas fig skin remained in a lower and more weakly varying range. This interpretation was strengthened by the DAEM-based predictive analysis, which showed that seed required a broader and more right-shifted distributed-reactivity representation, while skin was characterized by a lower-energy and more localized reactivity structure. Withheld-rate validation further demonstrated that these differences were preserved under unseen heating conditions, indicating that the seed–skin contrast can be captured in a reduced-order predictive model

Table 4

Screening gate-to-gate midpoint LCA results for fig seed- and fig skin-derived biochars produced under the five pyrolysis programmes.

Run	Sample	Climate change (kg CO ₂ -eq)	Resource use, fossils (MJ)	Water use (m ³ deprivation)	Acidification (mol H ⁺ eq)	Photochemical ozone formation (kg NMVOC eq)
1	F-SD1	2.653	29.31	1.820	0.0124	0.0051
2	F-SD2	1.936	21.39	1.328	0.0091	0.0037
3	F-SD3	1.003	11.08	0.688	0.0047	0.0019
4	F-SD4	1.649	18.22	1.132	0.0077	0.0031
5	F-SD5	1.338	14.78	0.918	0.0063	0.0026
1	F-SN1	2.652	29.30	1.820	0.0124	0.0051
2	F-SN2	1.936	21.38	1.328	0.0091	0.0037
3	F-SN3	1.004	11.09	0.689	0.0047	0.0019
4	F-SN4	1.650	18.22	1.132	0.0077	0.0031
5	F-SN5	1.339	14.79	0.918	0.0063	0.0026

Table 5

Integrated decision-support summary of fraction-resolved pyrolysis behavior, kinetic descriptors, predictive distributed-reactivity analysis, and screening environmental implications for fig seed- and fig skin-derived biochars.

Decision indicator	Fig seed	Fig skin	Decision implication within the tested severity matrix
Biochar yield response across severity programs	30.3% → 24.52% (mildest → most severe)	32.0% → 27.73% (mildest → most severe)	Yield decreases with severity for both fractions, but skin retains more solid than seed under matched programs.
Retention indices across severity (EY, CR)	Highest under mildest conditions (EY 43.78–45.06%, CR 44.64–45.83%); lower under severe conditions	Same overall trade-off across coded conditions	Mild conditions favor retention-type objectives, whereas increasing severity improves upgrading at the expense of retained energy and carbon.
DTG stage fingerprint (raw; Gaussian pseudo-stages over 150–500 °C)	Stage I (<260 °C): negligible; Stage III (≥400 °C): 0–52.17% (19.22–52.17% for $\beta = 10\text{--}40\text{ °C min}^{-1}$)	Stage I (<260 °C): 27.21–35.54%	Skin retains a persistent low-temperature devolatilization contribution, whereas seed shifts a larger share of decomposition toward later and higher-temperature regions.
Peak localization (raw; FWHM of dominant DTG feature)	≈101–118 °C (broad)	≈36–37 °C (narrow; nearly invariant)	Seed devolatilization is more temperature-distributed, whereas skin shows more localized and concentrated thermal decomposition.
Operational intensity descriptor (raw; CPI)	$8.799 \times 10^{-6} \rightarrow 5.240 \times 10^{-4}$ across β	$3.213 \times 10^{-5} \rightarrow 2.611 \times 10^{-3}$ across β	Under the same CPI definition, skin shows higher DTG-space process intensity, consistent with a more front-loaded decomposition profile.
Isoconversional Ea(α) band (raw; $\alpha = 0.1\text{--}0.9$)	Integral methods: ~107–110 → ~321–327 kJ mol ⁻¹ ; Friedman: 120.87 → 336.07 kJ mol ⁻¹	Integral methods: ~74–77 → ~149–151 kJ mol ⁻¹ ; Friedman: 54.54 → 141.35 kJ mol ⁻¹	Seed exhibits markedly higher and more conversion-sensitive apparent barriers, whereas skin remains within a lower and more stable Ea band.
Dominant kinetic-form tendency (Criado master plots; principal window $\alpha = 0.3\text{--}0.6$)	Power-law (P-type) highest; Avrami–Erofeev (A-type) next	Same ranking; modestly lower deviation for top-ranked functions	In the principal devolatilization window, both fractions show closest agreement with P/A families; deviations outside $\alpha \approx 0.3\text{--}0.6$ indicate conversion-window-dependent apparent form.
ATR–FTIR direction-of-change in chars (surface chemistry)	Stronger suppression of O–H and aliphatic C–H; more dominant condensed/aromatic region (1500–1600 cm ⁻¹)	Comparatively clearer oxygen-containing bands retained or reorganized under matched severity	Under identical severity, seed trends toward stronger aromatic condensation, whereas skin retains comparatively more oxygenated character.
Predictive distributed-reactivity pattern (DAEM; raw)	Broader and more right-shifted activation-energy distribution; dominant component near 158.1 kJ mol ⁻¹ ; withheld-rate TG RMSE 0.96–1.53%	Lower-energy and narrower distribution; components near 65.0 and 84.2 kJ mol ⁻¹ ; withheld-rate TG RMSE 1.34–1.83%	Seed shows broader and more resistant distributed reactivity, whereas skin shows a more localized and front-loaded decomposition pattern; this supports fraction-specific severity treatment rather than pooled processing.
Screening gate-to-gate LCA (biochars)	Program 3 gives the lowest midpoint burdens across categories; Program 1 the highest	Same ordering as seed; midpoint burdens are very similar under matched programs	Within the adopted process boundary, environmental burdens are driven mainly by programme-level electricity demand and duration rather than feedstock identity; Program 3 is the lowest-burden operating case.

rather than only in descriptive post hoc fitting. The screening gate-to-gate life-cycle assessment added a complementary environmental perspective. Within the adopted process boundary, midpoint burdens were governed primarily by programme-level electricity demand and duration rather than by feedstock identity, and Program 3 consistently emerged as the lowest-burden operating case for both fractions. Thus, while devolatilization behavior, kinetic structure, and surface chemistry were strongly fraction dependent, environmental hotspot results were mainly programme dependent.

Overall, the integrated yield, FTIR, TG–DTG, isoconversional, DAEM, and screening LCA evidence supports a fraction-specific severity framework for fig residues. Within this framework, skin-rich fractions are more favorable when higher char yield and retention of oxygenated functionality are prioritized, whereas seed-rich fractions are more favorable when stronger aromatic condensation and deeper carbonization are desired, albeit with greater late-stage kinetic resistance. Future work should test these fraction-resolved severity signatures against application-level performance metrics such as adsorption, soil response, electrochemical behavior, or anaerobic-digestion functionality.

Ethics statement for the use of human and animal subjects

Not applicable. This study involved no human participants or animal experiments.

Consent for publication

Not applicable.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this manuscript, the author(s) used ChatGPT (OpenAI) to improve language clarity and to refine the description and presentation of the modelling methodology (e.g., equations and calculation workflow). All analyses and numerical calculations were performed and verified by the authors, who reviewed and edited the text and take full responsibility for the content.

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Ahsanullah Soomro: Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Software, Visualization, Writing – original draft,

Writing – review & editing. **Anıl Tevfik Koçer**: Conceptualization, Data curation, Investigation, Resources, Validation, Writing – review & editing. **Didem Balkanlı**: Funding acquisition, Project administration, Resources, Supervision, Writing – review & editing.

Competing interest

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biombioe.2026.109556>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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